

MAGNETISM IN ROTATION, INVERSION AND VORTEX PHENOMENA ON THE EARTH

ABSTRACT

As a result of theoretical researches of the behavior of magnetic fields and currents in toroidal electromagnetic structures, called magnetoids by the author, which consist of a conductive sphere/ring and the surrounding toroidal magnetic field, the planet Earth was assigned to their number. The electromagnetic nature of the formation of the planet's geoid, its rotation and magnetic inversion has been shown.

The obtained conclusions were necessary to verify the presence and nature of the relationship between the state and dynamics of the Earth's magnetic field and various climatic phenomena observed on the planet.

Analyzing from the standpoint of electrodynamics the current location of the magnetic poles and the direction of rotation of the planet, it was revealed that the Earth today is in an inversion (abnormal) electromagnetic state. This is the main factor in the formation and dynamics of the current climate (the planet itself is a significant source of heat entering the atmosphere), intensification of tectonic and volcanic activity.

KEY WORDS: magnetic field, rotation, inversion, counter-inversion, vortex phenomena, climate.

ON THE MAGNETISM OF ROTATION, INVERSION AND VORTICES

As a result of theoretical researches of the behavior of magnetic fields and currents in toroidal electromagnetic (magnetic-current) structures of magnetoids, which consist of a (radially rotating) conductive sphere of the "body" and the surrounding toroidal magnetic field, it is possible to attribute the planet Earth to their number (Fig.1).

Fig.1. Representation of the toroidal electromagnetic structure of a magnetoid using the example of the planet Earth (Antarctica at the top)

The Earth's magnetic field is an integral and conditionally closed toroidal structure with its "visible" external and "invisible" internal components (Fig.2). The peripheral lines of the magnetic field intensity moving from the north magnetic pole to the south magnetic pole in the area of the south magnetic pole invisibly penetrate inside the planet, and from the south magnetic pole towards the north magnetic pole they return inside it, forming a single internal magnetic flow there called by the author as the "internal magnetic column".

Fig.2. Representation of the toroidal magnetic field using the example of magnetic fields and magnetic poles of a spiral current conductor (left) and a permanent magnet (right)

Here we will not touch on the nature of the origin of the Earth's magnetic field. The author has his own hypothesis, which will be presented separately. For now, let's look only at the behavior of magnetic fields and currents.

Also, without focusing on the consideration of rigid permanent magnets, which are a special case of the manifestation of magnetism, let's see how the magnetic field behaves in flexible flows. Indeed, in the theories of the formation of the Earth's magnetic field that are dominant today, the movement of flows is also considered. In this case, the rectified "internal magnetic column" must be shielded by currents (plasma/substance flows), which, wrapping around it, do not penetrate inside it. But this should turn the area of the "internal magnetic column" into an "internal current void" – a region of space, inside which currents are not formed, where particles are not able to get, where no matter can be located and formed; they only envelop such an "inner void" around.

The presence of the "internal magnetic column" area indicates that the planet should be by no means full-bodied inside: it should be hollow at least locally. Moreover, such a void is in a state of "current emptiness", what is equivalent to physical vacuum. Its limiting states are characterized by temperatures close to the temperature of absolute zero (-273°C).

Since there is no matter and currents in the "inner void", such a state can be equated to a state with a flow speed equal to zero. If we consider such a medium as an extremely rarefied ionized gas, then (according to Bernoulli's principle) it follows that the lower the current speed (liquid/gas flow), the higher the pressure; and the higher the pressure inside, the more it pushes outward. In other words, from the side of the "internal magnetic column" "pressure" can be created on the space surrounding it, filled with a substance moving radially around the "column". Together with centrifugal forces acting on the radially moving substance, this should lead to the expansion of the current "quasi-helix" (conductive sphere) surrounding the "internal magnetic column" and, accordingly, change the characteristics of the electromagnetic wave which is derivative from the magnetic field and currents. As a consequence, the region of the "central magnetic column" (the "inner void") of the planet should expand.

The stronger the magnetic field, the faster the radially oriented flows move in the conductive sphere, the higher the centrifugal forces, the more elongated along the equator and flattened from the poles will look like a body of matter surrounding the "internal magnetic column". So the planet acquires a spherical shape. In this case, the "internal magnetic column" also acquires a spherical shape, indicating that the area of the "internal void" inside the planet is also spherical. In other words, there are reasons to speak about the hollow geosphere of the planet, which resembles an inflated ball, and not a full-bodied glob. At the same time, the centrifugal movement of substance flows in the conductive sphere makes it possible to resist the "suction" forces of the "internal vacuum", maintaining the dense spherical shape of the conductive sphere and preventing it from collapsing.

Tendencies to expansion of the planet's geosphere with an increase in its magnetic field and, conversely, to the cessation of expansion and even compression (or stretching along the magnetic poles) as the magnetic field weakens, form the effect of its gradual self-expansion in the toroidal electromagnetic structure. It turns out that a planet endowed with a sufficient magnetic field should become larger and larger over time, that is, constantly "grow". To stop, slow down such growth or change its direction, up to destruction, the weakening or destruction (cessation) of the magnetic field can.

At the same time, the toroidal magnetic field has its own forces that can restrain the uncontrolled expansion of the "internal magnetic column" and the surrounding space (geosphere). Such forces of "cohesive resistance" are the peripheral magnetic lines of the same magnetic field and the "magnetic walls" formed by their aggregates.

Due to the mutual shielding and repulsion from the current in the opposite direction of the flow of the "internal magnetic column", the peripheral lines of the magnetic field connected with it into a single toroidal structure acquire an arcuate shape. However, the farther from the "internal magnetic column" the areas of peripheral magnetic lines are removed, the thinner their "magnetic thread" and the "magnetic wall" combined from their totality. They will be the thinnest in the region of the greatest distance from the poles – at the magnetic equator, while the densest – directly at the magnetic poles. Accordingly, the thinner the "magnetic thread", the denser the plasma flow wrapping around it.

In correlation with Bernoulli's principle, the thinner the line, the faster the flux flows along it. Therefore, the linear velocity of the magnetic flow in the peripheral lines must be higher than in the area of the "internal magnetic column". At the same time, in the plane of the magnetic equator, where the tension and straightening of the peripheral magnetic lines are the greatest, and the thickness is the smallest, the plasma flows flowing around them are the most dense and heated, what forms higher temperatures near the surface near the equator. Closer to the poles, where the intensity of magnetic lines and their density increases, on the contrary, the density of plasma flows decreases, and their linear velocity increases, resulting in a decrease in temperatures.

At the same time, the absolute pole of cold on the planet should be sought in the area of its northern magnetic pole, where the magnetic flow "poured out" from the area of the "internal magnetic column" and is not yet strongly "bound" by the plasma flows that meet it; while at the south magnetic pole the magnetic flow is already "getting rid" of the previously accumulated (warmer) plasma currents. Therefore, the extremely low temperatures near the south magnetic pole of the planet will be higher than the extremely low temperatures near its north magnetic pole. This is also confirmed by the results of available observations of temperatures near the Earth's poles.

Peripheral lines of intensity of the toroidal magnetic field (including due to the complexity and heterogeneity of the flows of substance in the conductive sphere, acquiring different electromagnetic characteristics of their own) form a series of consecutive "pure magnetic walls" around the planet. They are divided into several layers, both due to their shielding by separate plasma streams, and peripheral electric field lines flowing in the opposite direction, which form the separating/shielding "impure electromagnetic walls".

Inside the planet, as a magnetoid, there is a relative rotation of the current component (forming a current-conducting sphere of the flow of substance) around the axis of its magnetic component (the "internal magnetic column"). The trajectory of the electromagnetic wave (electric field helix) around the "internal magnetic column" of the planet, which depends on the electromagnetic characteristics of the flows in the conductive sphere, is a "thread" that determines the angular momentum of the conductive sphere inside the (conditionally stationary) toroidal magnetic field. Such a rotation can be perceived as a relative rotation of the planet's conductive sphere around the axis of its magnetic field (the "internal magnetic column").

In an ideal sphere, when the current-carrying flow is pulled into a narrow and long radial ring in the equatorial region, and also under ideal conditions, when external factors do not influence the conductive sphere, the electromagnetic wave length that determines the rotation parameters is π times greater than the distance between the poles, equal to the diameter sphere (as the ratio between the length of the circle encircling the sphere and its diameter, equal to $2\pi R / 2R = \pi$). Due to such a ratio, which can be considered a constant for an ideal sphere, a change in the size of the sphere does not lead to an increase in the angular velocity of its rotation. However, in real conditions, the flows inside the current-conducting sphere of the planet do not move in the form of an ideal radial ring, but in the form of spherical conductive layers with different speeds and flow around the contours of the inflated "internal magnetic column" in different ways. Therefore, in non-ideal cases, there are several overlapping electromagnetic waves with different characteristics (lengths and frequencies) at once, which affects the establishment of the planet's rotation speed, affects the deceleration or acceleration of its rotation around its axis.

The characteristics of the (resulting) electromagnetic wave that determines the speed of the planet's rotation depend not only on the size of the conductive sphere, but also on its composition, density, temperature, trajectories and flow rates in it, which are usually inhomogeneous. Also, the length of the electromagnetic wave of the planet is affected by the size of its solid crust, which blocks the free movement of current-generating flows or redirects them, the temperature characteristics of plasma flows in magma, in the World Ocean and the atmosphere of the planet, which are different layers separated by the "magnetic walls" of its toroidal electromagnetic structure. All this together determines the geometric characteristics of the planet's conductive sphere.

There is a connection between the intensity of the peripheral lines of the planet's magnetic field (correlating with the intensity of the "internal magnetic column") and the characteristics of its conductive sphere. The stronger the peripheral lines of the magnetic field, the faster the flows in the internal conductive sphere move, and the faster this conductive sphere rotates relative to the "internal magnetic column"; and vice versa.

When the peripheral "magnetic walls" cannot contain the pressure from the "internal magnetic column", a local rupture of the shell of the conductive sphere shielding it can occur. Such processes lead to volcanic and tectonic activity on the planet. Due to the design features of the planet's geosphere, such activity can be local or global. In other words, the main cause of tectonic and volcanic activity can be called the weakening of the peripheral magnetic lines and the magnetic field of the planet as a whole.

The protection mechanism for peripheral magnetic lines is the general strengthening of the Earth's magnetic field and its "internal magnetic column" while ensuring the natural flow of magnetic fluxes along all peripheral magnetic lines. Reducing the number of damage to the peripheral lines of the magnetic field contributes to maintaining its stable state. A protective mechanism for the peripheral "magnetic walls" can be cooling of the substance flowing through them and/or an increase in the speed of plasma flows along them.

The Ranque-Hilsch vortex effect can be explained by applying the logic of the interaction of the magnetic field, current and electric field, established by the author when considering the phenomena of superconductivity and plasma. This effect makes it possible to connect the dynamics of liquids and gases not only with thermodynamics, but also with electromagnetic phenomena.

It is known and experimentally established that the speed of liquid and gas flows increases as it approaches the cold end of the vortex system (vortex tube). Moreover, the greater the share of the cold flow in the total vortex circulation, the higher the average speed of its movement. And vice versa, the higher the velocity coefficient of the flow, the greater the proportion of its cold part. There is a dependence of the temperature gradient on the change in speed. On the example of the acceleration of a cold flow, the vortex effect can serve as evidence of an increase in the flow rate of a substance with a decrease in temperature. And vice versa, with an increase in local temperatures, the speed of the vortex flow in its corresponding sections can decrease.

Vortex and jet (helical) flows can be considered as structured. Consequently, in an accelerating structured flow (by analogy with the effect of superconductivity), a corresponding increase in conductivity and magnetic field strength should occur. This implies a relationship between a decrease in temperature and an increase in conductivity, an increase in flow speed, and an increase in the magnetic field. Conversely, an increase in temperature leads to a decrease in conductivity, a slowdown in the flow speed, and a weakening of the magnetic field (similar is observed in plasma phenomena). An increase in temperature and the thermal radiation associated with it is a consequence and evidence of the release of excess energy for such a state of energy from the magnetically active state of the system.

In a vortex column and in a (helical) jet phenomenon, both an external (peripheral) heating magnetic flow and an internal cooling magnetic flow are present. The relationship of such flows should be considered like oppositely directed "long magnetic rods", which are not attracted to each other. Their mutual shielding contributes to the creation of a "magnetic corridor" inside the warm peripheral/ambient flow to promote the internal, colder, uniform and accelerating flow. At the hot end of such a vortex system, where an internal cooling flow begins to form, the heated external flow is purified by ejecting impurities from it.

Structured vortices and jet streams are a kind of "electric machines" that can act as both "motors" and "generators" of electric current and magnetic field. The structuring of laminar or chaotic flows into helical or vortex ones leads to the transformation of flows into a kind of magnetoactive plasma and the appearance in them (albeit a similarity) of a magnetic field. By means of the magnetic field, the relationship between the dynamics of liquids and gases in structured flows and electrostatics is manifested. Hence, the phenomena described by Bernoulli's principle and its consequences have their own explanation from the standpoint of electromagnetism and can be applied not only to the dynamics of liquids and gases, but also to electrostatics and magnetism.

Forced creation (including due to shielding from the external environment) of a structured flow of liquid or gas in a linear direction (in a conditional pipe) makes such a flow similar to a magnetically active plasma or a superconducting flow. Structuring a laminar flow of a liquid or gas into such a "pipe" increases the linear velocity of its movement and reduces the pressure in it, and, hence, the resistance of the external environment. The increase in speed in the relatively closed space of the "pipe" leads to the gradual formation of a helical rotation of the moving stream; and the faster such a stream moves, the more it twists into a helix, absorbing heat and energy.

All flows of substance in the geosphere, oceans and atmosphere of the Earth function according to this principle. All of them thus form numerous local magnetic fields and anomalies, which, strengthening or weakening each other, are components of the resulting magnetic field of the planet.

The planet, as the toroidal electromagnetic structure, is a magnetic dipole having two opposite magnetic poles. Periodically, in such dipole structures, a magnetic field inversion can naturally occur – a reversal of the north and south magnetic poles, which can be due to both external and internal causes and factors. In terms of the magnetic inversion of the planet, an explanation of the causes and mechanisms must be sought, first of all, in inertia.

According to the right-hand rule, in the normal electromagnetic state of the toroidal electromagnetic structure, its current helicity (the direction of rotation of the conductive sphere) will be left-handed towards the planet's north magnetic pole, and the magnetic flow will be right-handed. In other words, if, looking from the northern magnetic field of the planet, its rotation occurs to the left, then the planet is in a normal (or counter-inversion) electromagnetic state, when the movement of currents is consistent with the state of the magnetic field. If at the same time the planet rotates to the right, then it is in an abnormal (inversion) electromagnetic state, when the currents conflict with the state of the magnetic field, counteracting it.

An inversion does not mean the complete disappearance of the magnetic field and leaving the planet without protection, even in the event of its significant weakening. However, significant transformations can occur in the conductive component of the planet: in the geosphere, oceans and atmosphere.

Inside the toroidal electromagnetic structure, due to inertia, including due to the preservation of the gyroscopic effect of the rotating system in it, changes in the conductive sphere of the planet (in the geosphere and oceans), as well as in the atmosphere, including during magnetic inversion, occur more slowly than in magnetic field.

If for some external or internal reasons there was a magnetic inversion in the magnetoid, then the direction of the helicity of the magnetic field will coincide with the direction of rotation of the conductive sphere, which leads the planet into a state of electromagnetic imbalance – into an abnormal electromagnetic state. However, having come into conflict with the laws of electrostatics, the electromagnetic balance is looking for the possibility of restoration at a new level.

In an abnormal (inversion) electromagnetic state, there is a gradual weakening and slowing down of flows in the conductive sphere (geosphere and/or atmosphere), since now the flows of substance do not move in the general magnetic flow, but against it, generating local magnetic fields which are derivative of such flows and counteract the general magnetic field of the planet. In this case, the weakening of the flow component does not lead to a sharp total stop of the magnetic field, but only to a gradual decrease in its intensity, along with a decrease in the flow speed in the conductive sphere. "Braking" of a magnetic flow by a unidirectional flow of substance manifests itself, among other things, in a gradual decrease in the strength of the peripheral magnetic lines of

the toroidal magnetic field and, consequently, in a proportional slowdown of the magnetic flow speed in the "internal magnetic column".

The deceleration of the magnetic flow in the "internal magnetic column" due to the rotation of the conductive sphere conflicting with the laws of electrodynamics leads to an increase in internal pressure on the conductive spatial sphere from both the "internal magnetic column" and the surrounding substance flows, which also slow down. So slowing down the speed of movement of flows in the current-carrying sphere of the planet automatically leads to the expansion (increase in diameter and volume) of its geosphere and an increase in pressure from the inside on its shell. Among other things, this is manifested in plasma ejections, an increase in tectonic and volcanic activity. Thus, an increase in internal pressure on the spatial sphere and (local or even complete) physical destruction of the toroidal electromagnetic structure of the magnetoid is a consequence of its magnetic field being in an inversion state.

Expansion processes in the flowing substance indicate not only a decrease in the speed of its movement, but also the simultaneous release of excess heat, which forms the conditions for the subsequent cooling of the planet. Evidence of approaching tendencies cooling the planet is an increase in the ambient temperature, for which heat comes mainly from within the conductive spatial sphere (from the flowing substance) of the planet. This usually manifests itself in the heating of the atmosphere and oceans – the space between the surface of the conductive sphere and the peripheral lines of the magnetic field, filled with shielding plasma flows.

The released heat is redistributed within the conductive sphere (geosphere), and is also transferred to the oceans and atmosphere in the form of electromagnetic radiation. As the heat is redistributed between the geosphere, oceans and atmosphere of the planet, their electromagnetic and, accordingly, magnetic characteristics change, that is, between the layers of a complex toroidal electromagnetic structure, its current and magnetic components, what makes it more prone to the occurrence of magnetic counter-inversion conditions.

When the toroidal electromagnetic structure returns to its normal magnetic state after the counter-inversion, when the interaction of the magnetic field of the planet and its conductive sphere is consistent with the laws of electrodynamics, conditions arise for amplification (increase in speed) of flows in the planet's conductive sphere, as well as a gradual increase in the magnetic field and its peripheral lines. This will lead to a decrease in the pressure of the "internal magnetic column" on the conductive sphere and the pressure from the conductive sphere on its outer shell (mainly in the equatorial plane). The accelerated movement of streams in the current-conducting sphere of the planet leads to an increase in their (electrical) shielding tendencies, which will help to retain heat inside the streams, cool them and "absorb" heat from the outside, that is, to cool the oceans and atmosphere. As a result, there will be a tendency to lower temperatures in the atmosphere and oceans, which will mean the beginning of an era of cooling on the planet. The onset of glaciers is a consequence of the normal (counter-inversion) state of the planet's magnetic field.

So the change in temperature gradients and the redistribution of heat leads to changes in the internal magnetic moment of the toroidal electromagnetic structure of the planet, creating the prerequisites for the emergence of new magnetic inversions and counter-inversions. The more actively the processes of heat exchange between the flowing substance in the current-conducting sphere and in the magnetosphere region take place, the more often the phenomena of inversion and counter-inversion will be observed.

As a result of magnetic inversion and counter-inversion, the direction and nature of flows in the geosphere, but, first of all, in the oceans and atmosphere of the planet, should change, with corresponding changes in thermal and electromagnetic phenomena, primarily at the poles.

If you look at the geographic south pole of the Earth, near which the planet's north magnetic pole is located today, the Earth rotates in a right-handed twist. This suggests that today our planet is in its inversion (abnormal) electromagnetic state. This is largely due to the observed global warming (the planet itself is a significant source of heat entering the atmosphere and oceans), increased tectonic and volcanic activity on Earth. So our planet is gradually preparing to restore its normal (counter-reversal) magnetic state.